

Advancements and Challenges in Stem Cell-Based Therapy for Diabetic Foot Ulcer

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Abstract: Diabetic foot ulcer (DFU) presents a significant complication of diabetes mellitus and poses a formidable medical challenge. Traditional treatments have fallen short in sufficiently reducing amputation rates associated with DFU. Stem cell-based therapy has been under investigation for managing DFU in recent years. This therapy's mechanism involves promoting angiogenesis, releasing paracrine factors, inducing vascular differentiation, dampening inflammation, enhancing collagen deposition, and modulating the immune response. However, determining the most suitable type and source of stem cells, as well as the optimal method of administration, remains a complex task. Various types and sources of stem cells, along with different administration routes, have been studied for DFU treatment. Diabetes may also adversely affect patients' stem cells, diminishing the efficacy of autologous stem cell transplantation and necessitating a compatible donor. Angioplasty may complement stem cell therapy, while scaffolds have shown promise in facilitating DFU healing through stem cell-based therapy. Although stem cell-based therapy holds promise as a regenerative medicine approach, conclusive evidence from well-designed studies is necessary to establish its safety, effectiveness, appropriate dosage, and optimal administration route.

Introduction: Diabetes mellitus stands as a pressing global health concern, representing a paramount medical emergency worldwide. Characterized by elevated blood glucose levels, diabetes can precipitate severe damage to vital organs including the heart, blood vessels, eyes, soft tissues, kidneys, and nerves. Vascular complications emerge as the most prevalent and serious manifestations of diabetes mellitus, serving as a primary cause of morbidity and mortality in afflicted individuals. If left unchecked, these complications may escalate into dyslipidemia, hyperglycemia, and insulin resistance, exacerbating the risk of atherosclerosis—a condition marked by the accumulation of lipid plaques within arteries, significantly reducing life expectancy, particularly in diabetic patients. Notably, diabetic retinopathy and nephropathy loom as significant contributors to blindness.

Efforts aimed at preventing vascular complications in diabetic patients emphasize intensive blood glucose management, which concurrently mitigates risks associated with nephropathy and retinopathy, alongside the adoption of antihypertensive medications and statin therapy, often integrated into the standard management of diabetes mellitus. However, insulin resistance and its repercussions across diverse tissues may wield greater influence than hyperglycemia alone in fostering atherothrombotic complications, particularly evident in type 2 diabetes. Thus, diabetes mellitus transcends being merely a disorder of carbohydrate metabolism; it serves as a chief instigator of vascular diseases that can afflict blood vessels of various types and sizes.

Moreover, diabetes mellitus precipitates microangiopathy within the colon, a condition more prevalent in diabetics than non-diabetic individuals. Compounding these challenges are frequent foot infections, which pose substantial morbidity and occasional mortality risks, necessitating intensive resource utilization encompassing antibiotic regimens and surgical interventions. Diabetic foot ulcers (DFU) represent a particularly distressing complication, characterized by ulceration in conjunction with neuropathy and/or peripheral artery disease (PAD) in diabetic patients. Annually, approximately 26 million individuals worldwide suffer from DFUs, with an additional 130 million at risk of developing diabetic peripheral neuropathy. Alarmingly, 25% of moderate to severe DFUs culminate in amputation, rendering DFU the foremost cause of global disability, significantly compromising quality of life.

Given its multifaceted etiology, the management of diabetic foot ulcers poses considerable challenges. Even upon successful ulcer healing, recurrence rates remain staggering, with approximately 40% recurrence within the first year and 65% within the initial 3 years post-healing. Standard treatment modalities for DFUs entail optimizing blood flow, debridement, infection control, and offloading. Despite these interventions, only half of the patients achieve healing within 20 weeks, with 50% experiencing recurrence within 18 months, underscoring the urgent need for enhanced therapeutic approaches.

Figure 1

Risk factors associated with the DFU

Treatment Therapies for Diabetic Foot Ulcers

Diabetic foot ulcers (DFUs) typically arise from a convergence of multiple risk factors. Neuropathy, peripheral artery disease (PAD), and foot deformities, when combined with external trauma like ill-fitting footwear or minor foot injuries, can gradually culminate in DFUs. The primary objective of DFU management is prompt wound closure, aiming to address DFUs at an early stage to facilitate rapid healing. Essential components of DFU management encompass treating the underlying disease etiology, ensuring adequate blood circulation, controlling local wound infections, and relieving pressure on the affected area. Effective foot care practices also play a pivotal role in DFU management.

Addressing the underlying disease processes commences with identifying the root cause of the ulcer and educating the patient about the issue. For instance, prompt treatment of severe ischemia is paramount for wound healing, irrespective of other interventions. Patients presenting with acute limb ischemia, characterized by rest pain, ulceration, or tissue loss, warrant referral for consideration of arterial reconstruction. Another crucial strategy involves achieving optimal diabetic management through strict glycemic control and addressing other risk factors such as hypertension, hyperlipidemia, and smoking. Additionally, managing nutritional deficiencies assumes significance.

Furthermore, it is imperative to investigate the physical cause of trauma and conduct a thorough foot examination. This entails assessing the appropriateness of footwear, identifying signs of wear and tear, and detecting any foreign bodies that could contribute to foot trauma. Ensuring adequate blood supply to the foot emerges as another critical aspect of DFU management. Acute limb ischemia constitutes a medical emergency and requires timely intervention to mitigate the risk. Consequently, revascularization is indicated in cases of critical limb ischemia, diminished perfusion, or impaired circulation to facilitate and sustain healing and avert or delay future amputations.

Moreover, emphasis should be placed on regular foot inspections, bacterial control, and maintaining an optimal moisture balance to prevent maceration. Wound management strategies, including tissue debridement, inflammation, and infection control, also play pivotal roles in promoting wound healing.

Wound Dressing- Good wound dressing protects ulcer from the external environment, thus preventing possible infection, relieving symptoms, and facilitating healing. Wound dressing must be taken as an adjuvant therapy as it cannot substitute medically proven curative approaches although it constitutes a part of the treatment in DFUs. Depending on the physiology of the lesion, numerous types of wound dressing are currently in existence. Moreover, currently, no single wound dressing product achieves the physiological needs for proper healing of DFU.

One of the gold standards in aiding wound healing, notably favouring the healing process of wounds, including diabetic foot ulcers. Regular foot examination, patient education, simple hygiene practices, use of an appropriate footwear, and the prompt treatment of minor injuries can reduce the occurrence of ulcers drastically, and reduces the need for major limb amputation in a non-ischemic limb.

Figure 2

Conventional DFU treatments

Off-Loading -As for pressure offloading, it is very important to offload the point of wound areas of the foot in patients with peripheral neuropathy in order to redistribute pressures evenly. Insufficient offloading leads to tissue damage and worsening of the ulceration. The gold standard strategy for offloading is the Total Contact Cast (TCC), if properly applied, it distributes pressures evenly over the plantar surface of the foot. TCC is not easy to be removed by the patient, thereby ensuring compliance and reduces healing time.

The chances of skin irritation and further ulcers can emerge if the TCC is applied improperly.

Figure 3

Negative Pressure Wound Therapy- Negative wound therapy is a result of the medical technological advancements in the field of wound dressing and care. It has a unique capacity healing, covering a range of acute and chronic

Total contact casting (TCC) is a specially designed cast designed to take weight off of the foot (off-loading) in patients with diabetic foot ulcers (DFUs). Reducing pressure on the wound by taking weight off the foot has proven to be very effective in DFU treatment (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Total_contact_casting)

pressure advanced of wound wounds.

NPWT is a therapeutic technique of using a vacuum to promote wound healing in acute or chronic conditions, reduces oedema, enhances microcirculation, improves tissue growth & contracts wound. The vacuum machine, automatically sucks the tissue fluids into a canister. The tissue fluids contain bioactive substances such as inflammatory cytokines and proteases, which contribute to wound healing negatively. In addition, if the wound is left unchecked, the tissue fluids or exudates become a favourable ground for the infectious pathogens to grow, thus posing a danger for the development of sepsis. The use of negative pressure wound therapy reduces the frequency of wound dressing and, consequently, prevent unnecessary exposure to the un-favourable environment. If required, antibiotics along with saline can also be pushed into the wound for better and speedy would healing.

The device has its own contraindications such as, Necrotic tissue with eschar, Untreated osteomyelitis, Wounds with unexplored / visible fistula, Presence of untreated coagulopathy / Clotting disorder, Wounds including open joint capsules, compromised micro-vascular blood flow to wound.

Figure 4

Negative Pressure Wound Therapy

Wound Debridement- Wound debridement is a procedure that involves the removal of nonviable or infected wound tissues to provide a conducive environment for the regeneration of healthy tissue. It is carried out using a curette and scissors where chronic wound is converted into an acute wound. Depending on the tissue type, debridement can be accomplished using Surgical, Autolytic, Enzymatic, Mechanical, and Biological techniques

- **Surgical/ Sharps Debridement:** *The debridement is performed with sterile surgical instruments such as curettes or scalpels by the healthcare provider. The technique/ procedure, quickly removes devitalized tissue from the wound bed leaving healthy tissue intact and can be performed in a wound clinic or at the bedside. Surgical debridement is more aggressive and is performed in an operating room and may be non-selective removing healthy tissue as well as devitalized tissue.*
- **Enzymatic Debridement:** *This debridement method is performed by applying an enzyme enriched topical preparation to the wound bed that helps to liquify devitalized tissue. These are less painful than a surgical/sharps debridement. The negative to this therapy is the high cost of the enzymatic preparation.*
- **Mechanical Debridement:** *This type of debridement can be achieved through wet-to-dry dressings or hydrotherapy. It is usually a painful treatment. This process removes viable and devitalized tissue from the wound bed.*
- **Biological Debridement:** *This is the use of sterile maggots, *Lucilia sericata* (the green bottle fly) to debride wounds. The maggots are grown in a sterile environment and are applied to the wound bed.*
- **Autolytic Debridement:** *This is a commonly used debridement modality. Autolytic debridement is painless and uses dressings to promote moist wound healing. The wound dressing provides a moisture balanced environment that allows the body's natural enzymes to liquify devitalized tissue. The procedure is slow, but the benefit of decreased pain, easy to apply dressings, and lack of trauma to the wound bed makes this a commonly used debridement method.*

The debridement techniques lack quality and comparative effectiveness due to imprecision and methodologic limitations, Consequently, available expertise, clinical context, procedural cost, and patient choice dictate the choice of the debridement method.

Challenges on Diabetic Foot Ulcer and Healing Process.

Wound healing is an aggressive-convoluted process that gets established when the tissue integrity is compromised. The normal stages of healing materialize in acute wound are noticeable indicators of healing and are observed within 30 days. In a DM subjects, metabolic disturbances, infections, and occlusive vascular lesions derail the timely transition of wound healing phases by prolonging or locking in a particular phase, thus leading to chronicity or lesion enlargement.

Figure 5

Mechanism of wound healing and dysregulation of diabetic foot ulcers. The stages of wound healing and dysregulation of diabetic foot ulcers: Wound healing begins with hemostasis phase, where a platelet plug prevents blood loss and a preliminary fibrin matrix is formed. Inflammation phase ensues to avoid infection (phagocytosis), with the secretion of neutrophils, macrophages, cytokines, and growth factors to remove cell debris. During the proliferative phase, endothelial cells, macrophages, fibroblast, and keratinocytes cells accelerate angiogenesis by closing the wound gap and replacing the initial fibrin clot with granulation tissue. Finally, the remodeling phase causes overall wound contraction by secretion of myofibroblasts and macrophages maturation. In diabetic wounds, active diabetes interrupts routine wound-healing phases, leading to poor outcomes. (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Total_contact_casting)

Stem Cell:

Human body is comprising of trillion of cells, making stem cells extremely important to human development.

The use of stem cells to treat human disease is being investigated within scientific research, as well as thousands of clinical trials worldwide. These cells are bringing hope to patients, researchers, and clinicians. Stem cells provide new cells for the body as it grows, and replace specialised cells that are damaged or lost. These cells have the property of, dividing over and over again to produce new cells and, while dividing, they change into the other types of cells that make up the human body.

What Are Stem Cells?

Stem cells are undifferentiated cells with the capacity to both differentiate and multiply into the 200 cells types that form a human being.

Stem Cell Therapy: Progressive developments in the field of stem cell therapy (SCT) are the immense developments in the field of medical treatment and rehabilitation in human beings. The conventional treatment for diabetic foot ulcer is mainly medical treatment and surgical intervention for blood flow reconstruction. However, medical treatment alone cannot solve the problem when it comes to foot ischemia caused by arterial stenosis and occlusion. Surgical treatment also faces some problems to restore the blood flow in some cases. Preferred methods for lower limb ischemia management are percutaneous angioplasty and stent therapies. These procedures are difficult to perform in below-the-knee long segment lesions in patients with microvascular pathology, as many patients lack the distal arterial outflow tract, and the lower extremity artery lesions in DFU involve the lower leg artery. For this reason, DFU patients face a risk of amputation, as they are unable to receive interventional therapy for arterial bypass, which is also a risk in specific patients that suffer cardiovascular and cerebrovascular diseases.

Innovative and effective therapies have been developed to help repair chronic wounds; these therapies include topical applications of growth factors and cell-based therapies. Even though both the growth factors and stem cell therapies have a shortcoming in fully repairing DFU, stem cell therapy still has an advantage over growth factors in DFU. Stem cells can regulate tissue regeneration in an all-around way by refining the microenvironment at the wound site. It has been reported that stem cells can have an influence on many pathophysiological processes such as ulcer healing by stimulating the tissue repair cell activities, increasing the synthesis of the extracellular matrix, and promoting angiogenesis in the ischemic tissue.

Animal studies have proven that stem cell implantation results in improved blood flow circulation in ischemic limbs. Moreover, recent studies have reported that stem cell therapy could reduce amputation rate in DFU. In addition, stem cells play a major role in post-injury and routine homeostasis skin repair. Stem cell therapy has evolved as a new technique for treating diabetic lower limb ischemic disease, and specifically, diabetic foot ulcer.

Stem cell therapy aims to support wound healing by stimulating the formation of new blood vessels that increase blood supply and relieve limb ischemia. The role of stem cells is better expressed in repairing damage after being administered to traditional treatment, leading to improvement in management of complications of DFU.

Stem cells treatment therapy include Autologous (*own cells*), Allogeneic (*Other than the patient*), and Xenotransplantation cells (*Animal source*)

Autologous stem cell therapy (ASCT): Is a promising therapy for ulcer healing, especially in lower extremity chronic wounds.

The first human trial in 2002 suggested that bone marrow mononuclear cell implantation is effective and safe for therapeutic angiogenesis in patients even with critical limb ischemia and shows complete ulcer healing and reducing limb amputation.

Autologous stem cell therapy (ASCT) emerges as a

promising strategy for ulcer healing, particularly in lower extremity chronic wounds. ASCT represents a groundbreaking approach to medical treatment, harnessing the body's inherent regenerative abilities to address a wide array of health conditions.

Stem cells, revered for their extraordinary capacity to differentiate into diverse cell types and self-renew, play a pivotal role in regenerative medicine. ASCT entails the extraction of stem cells from the patient's own body, often sourced from bone marrow or adipose tissue. These stem cells are then isolated, processed, and reintroduced into the patient to stimulate healing and tissue regeneration.

A key advantage of ASCT lies in its compatibility with the patient's immune system, thereby minimizing the risk of rejection or adverse reactions. By utilizing the patient's own cells, ASCT obviates the need for immunosuppressive drugs, enhancing the treatment's safety profile.

The applications of ASCT are wide-ranging and encompass various medical conditions, including orthopedic injuries, neurological disorders, autoimmune diseases, cardiovascular conditions, and chronic wounds like diabetic foot ulcers. Stem cells' versatility and regenerative properties make them particularly well-suited for addressing degenerative diseases and tissue damage.

In orthopedic injuries, ASCT involves the direct injection of stem cells into the injury site to promote tissue repair, alleviate pain, and enhance joint function. Clinical studies have demonstrated its effectiveness in promoting cartilage regeneration and facilitating musculoskeletal injury healing.

Neurological disorders represent another area of interest for ASCT, with stem cells offering the potential to replace damaged neurons and promote neural regeneration. Preliminary studies have shown promising results in improving motor function and neurological outcomes in patients with conditions such as Parkinson's disease and spinal cord injuries.

For autoimmune diseases, ASCT provides a novel approach to modulating the immune system and inducing disease remission. By reprogramming the immune response using the patient's own stem cells, clinicians aim to effectively suppress autoimmune reactions.

Cardiovascular diseases, including myocardial infarction and chronic heart failure, also present a promising avenue for ASCT. Stem cells delivered directly to the heart tissue promote angiogenesis, improve cardiac function, and enhance myocardial regeneration.

Chronic wounds, such as diabetic foot ulcers, pose significant clinical challenges, and ASCT holds promise in enhancing tissue regeneration and promoting wound closure. By delivering stem cells directly to the ulcer site, clinicians aim to stimulate angiogenesis and accelerate tissue repair.

Despite its potential, ASCT faces challenges related to technical complexities, patient variability, and ethical considerations. However, ongoing advances in stem cell research and regenerative medicine offer hope for overcoming these challenges and further optimizing ASCT for improved patient outcomes.

Autologous stem cells used in therapy's include Bone Marrow-derived stem cells (BMSCs) such as, Bone marrow mesenchymal stem cells (BMMSCs) and Bone marrow mononuclear cells (BMMNCs), Peripheral blood-derived stem cells (PBSCs), Peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMNCs), Adipose-derived stem cells (ASCs), Human processed lipoaspirate (PLA), Bone marrow-enriched tissue repair cells (BMTRCs), and Autologous adipose-derived stromal vascular fraction (SVF) cells.

Bone Marrow-Derived Stem Cells (BMSCs):

Both BMMSCs and BMMNCs have shown potential in promoting wound healing by differentiating into various cell types involved in tissue repair, such as fibroblasts, endothelial cells, and keratinocytes. They also secrete growth factors and cytokines that stimulate angiogenesis, collagen deposition, and epithelialization.

Peripheral Blood-Derived Stem Cells (PBSCs):

PBMNCs can contribute to wound healing by releasing growth factors and cytokines that promote tissue regeneration and by differentiating into various cell types involved in the wound healing process.

Adipose-Derived Stem Cells (ASCs):

ASCs have been studied extensively for their regenerative potential in wound healing. They promote angiogenesis, collagen synthesis, and epithelialization, leading to improved wound closure and tissue regeneration.

Human Processed Lipoaspirate (PLA):

PLA, containing ASCs among other cellular components, has been utilized in wound healing therapies. The ASCs within PLA can accelerate wound closure, reduce inflammation, and enhance tissue regeneration.

Bone Marrow-Enriched Tissue Repair Cells (BMTRCs):

BMTRCs, due to their enriched composition, exhibit enhanced regenerative properties compared to regular bone marrow-derived cells. They contribute to wound healing by promoting angiogenesis, extracellular matrix deposition, and tissue remodelling.

Autologous Adipose-Derived Stromal Vascular Fraction (SVF) Cells:

SVF cells, including ASCs, release growth factors and cytokines that facilitate wound healing processes such as angiogenesis, collagen synthesis, and tissue remodelling. They can be applied directly to wounds or incorporated into tissue engineering constructs for enhanced wound repair.

In short, these various types of stem cells offer promising avenues for improving wound healing outcomes by promoting tissue regeneration, angiogenesis, and inflammation resolution. Their diverse mechanisms of action make them valuable tools in developing novel therapeutic approaches for acute and chronic wounds.

In a randomized study conducted by Lu et al., the effect of intramuscularly injected BMMNCs and BMMSCs in the treatment of chronic wounds in patients with diabetic critical limb ischemia and foot ulcers was compared [80]. The results showed that both cell types were able to decrease pain and improve perfusion on the ankle brachial index (ABI) and transcutaneous partial pressure of oxygen (TcPO₂). However, the ulcer-healing rate was significantly higher in the BMMSC treated group six weeks post injection, and 100% healing was reached four weeks earlier than in the BMMNC group.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/21216483/>

Route of administration for MSC therapy

Based on the information provided, here are the different routes of administration for Mesenchymal Stem Cell (MSC) therapy, along with their advantages and challenges:

Local Delivery:

- Topical Application: Directly applying MSCs onto the wound surface.
- Topical Injection: Injecting MSCs directly into the wound bed.
- Scaffold and Gel: Incorporating MSCs into scaffolds or gels for controlled release at the wound site.

Advantages: Direct delivery to the affected area, promoting localized tissue regeneration.

Challenges: Poor cell localization, potential damage to cell viability during injection, and limited effectiveness in penetrating deep wounds.

Systemic Delivery:

- Intravenous Administration: Infusing MSCs into the bloodstream.
- Arterial Administration: Delivering MSCs through arteries, targeting specific organs or tissues.

Advantages: Wide distribution throughout the body, potential systemic effects beyond the target area.

Challenges: Most cells accumulate in the lungs, limited migration to the ulcer site, and potential dilution of therapeutic effect due to distribution throughout the body.

Intramuscular Injection:

- Administering MSCs directly into muscle tissue.

Advantages: Improved effectiveness for diabetic foot treatment, potentially enhancing tissue regeneration.

Challenges: Limited to localized treatment, may not reach deep ulcers effectively.

Intradermal Injection:

- Injecting MSCs into the skin surrounding the wound.

Advantages: Improved wound healing process, enhanced tissue regeneration at the wound edge.

Challenges: Limited to the wound periphery, may not address deep ulceration.

To address challenges associated with local delivery, researchers are exploring the use of supportive excipients such as 3D printed collagen, chitosan, polyurethane scaffolds, and cell gels to improve cell viability and effective maintenance time for topical application preparations of MSCs.

Ultimately, the choice of administration route should be tailored to individual patient needs, considering factors such as the severity and location of the wound, patient health status, and resource availability. Personalized treatment plans can optimize therapeutic outcomes in MSC therapy for diabetic foot and other conditions.

Figure 6

The route of administration for mesenchymal stem cells therapy. Mesenchymal stem cells are mainly used for the treatment of diabetic foot by local delivery and systemic delivery. Local delivery is divided into topical application, topical injection, scaffold, gel and so on; systemic delivery is divided into intravenous administration and arterial administration.

(<https://stemcellres.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13287-018-0938-6>)

Mechanisms of MSCs in the treatment of diabetic foot

Mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) have emerged as promising candidates for the treatment of diabetic foot ulcers (DFUs) due to their multifaceted mechanisms that contribute to wound healing and tissue regeneration. Understanding the intricate processes underlying MSC-mediated therapeutic effects provides insights into their efficacy in DFU management.

Cell proliferation, differentiation, and migration are fundamental processes involved in the physiological repair of DFU wounds. Upon tissue damage, a cascade of events is triggered to initiate wound repair mechanisms. Growth factors and cytokines play pivotal roles in coordinating cellular responses, including proliferation, differentiation, migration, and protein synthesis. Recent research has highlighted the significance of various growth factors and molecular mechanisms in DFU pathogenesis and repair, underscoring the potential of MSCs in providing a repertoire of growth factors essential for wound healing.

A critical aspect contributing to diabetic foot complications is vascular damage and impaired angiogenesis. The formation and regeneration of new blood vessels in the DFU area are crucial for supplying nutrients to granulation tissue and facilitating wound closure. MSCs have been shown to secrete a diverse array of cytokines, including vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), basic fibroblast growth factor (bFGF), stromal cell-derived factor-1 (SDF-1), keratinocyte growth factor 2 (KGF-2), insulin-like growth factor 1 (IGF-1), placental growth factor (PIGF), and epidermal growth factor (EGF). These factors exert potent pro-angiogenic effects, enhancing microvascular perfusion and promoting neovascularization, thereby facilitating wound healing in DFUs.

The secretion of VEGF by MSCs is particularly noteworthy, as VEGF is a key regulator of angiogenesis and vascular permeability. By stimulating endothelial cell proliferation, migration, and tube formation, VEGF promotes the formation of functional blood vessels essential for tissue repair. Similarly, bFGF acts synergistically with VEGF to enhance angiogenesis and accelerate wound closure. SDF-1 plays a pivotal role in recruiting endothelial progenitor cells to the site of injury, contributing to neovascularization and tissue regeneration.

Furthermore, MSC-derived growth factors such as KGF-2, IGF-1, PIGF, and EGF exert trophic effects on keratinocytes and fibroblasts, promoting epithelialization and collagen synthesis, essential processes in wound closure and tissue remodeling.

Overall, the multifaceted paracrine effects of MSCs, mediated by the secretion of various growth factors and cytokines, contribute to their therapeutic efficacy in DFU treatment. By promoting angiogenesis, enhancing tissue regeneration, and facilitating wound closure, MSC-based therapies offer promising avenues for improving outcomes in patients with diabetic foot complications. Further research into the mechanistic aspects of MSC-mediated wound healing is warranted to optimize their clinical application and maximize therapeutic benefits for individuals with DFUs.

Limitations and Recommendations

Stem cell therapy holds immense promise in the realm of medical treatment, offering potential solutions for various ailments and conditions. However, like any evolving field, it is essential to acknowledge its limitations and areas for improvement to ensure the credibility and efficacy of its applications.

One significant limitation in the assessment of stem cell therapy's efficacy is the short follow-up periods in many studies. The duration of follow-up plays a crucial role in understanding the long-term effects and sustainability of the treatment. Without sufficient long-term data, it becomes challenging to draw definitive conclusions regarding the lasting benefits or potential risks associated with stem cell therapy.

Moreover, the scarcity of randomized-controlled trials (RCTs) in the literature poses another obstacle. RCTs are considered the gold standard in clinical research as they minimize bias and provide robust evidence for treatment efficacy. The limited number of RCTs available for review undermines the strength of the evidence supporting stem cell therapy.

Furthermore, the small sample sizes of the studies included in the review paper raise concerns about the generalizability of the findings. Studies with small sample sizes may not accurately represent the broader population, leading to skewed results and unreliable conclusions. To address this limitation, future research endeavors should aim for larger sample sizes to enhance the statistical power and validity of the findings.

The lack of standardized methods for stem cell administration across studies is another challenge. Each research team may employ different techniques and protocols for cell delivery, making it difficult to compare outcomes and draw consistent conclusions. Standardization of administration methods is essential for ensuring reproducibility and facilitating data synthesis across studies.

Despite significant advancements in stem cell research, the absence of convincing data from rigorously conducted multicenter RCTs remains a glaring gap. Multicenter RCTs involve collaboration among multiple research institutions, offering greater diversity in patient populations and enhancing the reliability of the results. Strict monitoring and

adherence to standardized protocols are critical components of multicenter trials, ensuring the credibility and generalizability of the findings.

Moving forward, concerted efforts are needed to address these limitations and enhance the quality of stem cell research. Researchers should prioritize conducting long-term studies with adequate follow-up periods, increasing the number of RCTs with larger sample sizes, and standardizing methods for stem cell administration. Collaborative initiatives involving multiple research centers are vital for achieving these objectives and advancing the field of stem cell therapy.

Conclusions

In conclusion, while stem cell therapy holds immense promise for medical treatment, it is essential to recognize and address its limitations to realize its full potential. By overcoming these challenges through rigorous research and collaborative efforts, we can pave the way for safer, more effective, and widely applicable stem cell therapies in the future. Stem cell therapy has been used as adjuvant therapy in the treatment of diabetic foot ulcers. We did not notice any significant differences in the healing effects between AD-MSCs and BM-MSCs. Furthermore, the results portrayed in this study clearly demonstrate that the application of mesenchymal stem cells is safe and efficacious with no clinically visible adverse effects and may therefore help prevent major limb amputations in uncomplicated diabetic foot ulcers. However, there are still several challenges with consensus on

the most applicable cell type, route of administration, and dosages. These are some of the significantly prevailing hindrances in conventionalizing the use of stem cells for this purpose.

Risk factors associated with the development of diabetic foot ulcers (DFUs) (produced using BioRender). The chronic low-grade inflammation and prolonged hyperglycemia in individuals with diabetes can foster myelin damage over time, prompting peripheral neuropathy. This results in oxidative stress and impairment of the sensitive, motor, and autonomous nerves. In turn, peripheral arterial disease (PAD) leads to insufficient blood supply and subsequent hypoxia, as well as hypercoagulability and serious limb ischemia, weakening the lower-extremity zones and making them prone to secondary infections. On top of that, angiogenesis is also reduced in individuals with diabetes. Foot ulceration is hence expectable.

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